

Book Review

Dal Yong Jin, *Global South Discourse in East Asian Media Studies*

Routledge, 2022; 178 pages

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Over the last ten to fifteen years, the cultural power of what is termed the “hallyu”, or “Korean Wave” has become ever more apparent in popular media discourses. The massive appeal of K-Pop, *Squid Game* and the films of Bong Joon Ho are all testament to the way that the transnational nature of digital media culture has seen the relationship between Western, capitalist media and the media produced by the countries of the Global South has changed irrevocably. It is this change that prompts Dal Yong Jin to offer this account of the way that East Asian media, culture and digital technology can be seen from a Global South perspective.

For the purposes of clarity, it is helpful to explain how the author sees both the term “Global South” and how they define East Asia. As Jin explains it is the much improved (but still imperfect) phrase for what were seen as “developing” or “third-world” countries. This is particularly significant because a number of East Asian countries (Korea, Japan, Taiwan, Singapore etc) are geographically positioned in the South, but economically they are aligned to the Global North, having as they do, developed industrial and technological infrastructures. Such tensions mean that Media Studies scholars need to create new theoretical perspectives on the way that East Asian media industries, platforms and texts might be seen in relation to Global South discourse, and it is – at least partly – that Jin is writing this book.

Fairly early on in the book, Jin positions the project of his enquiry in relation to wider media theory, noting that there is very little consideration of non-Western perspectives on East Asian media texts, partly because its complexity and diversity requires an

interdisciplinary approach which requires an encounter with area studies (Japanese Studies, Chinese Studies etc) which have not been forthcoming. However, the author is clear that such interdisciplinary work is essential to challenge Western hegemonies of theory and practice, and it is in this spirit that he continues to analyse East Asian Media culture.

With this in mind, the author explores a number of key themes which run through East Asian media studies; threads that are individually unique but are bound together in East Asia that create common ground for media scholars. Hybridity, Regionalization and Digital Culture are all presented as ways of fermenting media texts, industries and audiences which represent the particularity of that geography. Hybridity (or hybridization), for example is the way that Asian media cultures have merged Western media forms with local content to create new cultural phenomena. To some extent this has happened fairly constantly since the end of World War Two, but the author notes that what is different about recent history is that the interweaving of both the colonizer and the colonized, in cultural terms, has resulted in East Asian media culture having an increasing role to play in the cultural life of Western societies. Jin gives a great example of this in the book by analysing the work of Korean film director Bong Joon Ho; his film *Snowpiercer* originating in a French graphic novel, but then having director Bong's distinctly Korean aesthetic being applied to it to create a film which was sold back to American and European audiences. Jin's point about *Snowpiercer*, *Parasite* and *Squid Game* is that they are globally marketed media products, but they retain a distinctive, East Asian feel to them.

Similarly, regionalization, or "cultural collaboration" as Jin terms it, describes the kinds of economic and political relationships which allow for East Asian media industries to work together to produce texts which can then bring benefits to a number of different media economies. Jin explores licensing of TV formats as one such way this might occur, pointing out that many game show formats familiar to Western audiences (*Ninja Warrior*, *Hole in the Wall*, *Dragons Den* etc.) originate in strong collaborations by media companies across the East Asia region. This too is an example of way that the global south discourse of the media cultures in Japan, Korea, Malaysia and elsewhere has come to be influential in the global north.

To conclude then, *Global South Discourse in East Asian Media Studies* is a powerful exploration (explanation) of the way that East Asian media has become influential through turning its position within the wider geographical and political reality of the global south into one of great strength. It is a fascinating rumination on

the way that we in the West have seen (but also should see) both East Asia and the global south through its media cultures. It deals with quite a specialised and particularised media landscape for sure, but its perspective has many resonances for Western media cultures as well, and as such will be of great use and interest to many Media Studies scholars.